

New Etymologies for PIE **h₂ews* (“dawn”), PIE **h₂éwis* (“bird”), PIE **h₂ōwyóm* (“egg”), PIE **h₂ówis* (“sheep”), many of the PIE roots beginning with **D^h*; Proto-Indo-Iranian **mrgás* (“forest animal/wild animal”), Germano-Celtic **márkos* (“horse”, “wild horse”), Ancient Greek Νηρεύς (Nereus), γῆ, γᾶ, γαῖα (“earth”) et al.

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Introduction

Draft number 8, continuing the updates begun in the 5th or 6th edition, updates which I call “applying the knowledge of how the word-initial **h₂* phoneme was pronounced in PIE in order to determine the actual etymologies”, an endeavour which has totally changed many of the etymologies, but some---**h₂ōwyóm* (“egg”) and **h₂ówis* (“sheep”) for example---only needed a few adjustments: the words did refer to rounded masses, but they do not derive from “breath” and did not mean “swollen; infused with life-force” rather---well, you can read the work and see what I’m talking about.

Part 1.

I posit that Proto-Indo-Iranian **mrgás* (defined in the references as meaning “a forest animal”) derives from an Eteo-IE root **mVr* (V=“vowel undetermined”) that meant “force”, leading to meanings such as “spiritfull, lively, vigorous, powerful, fierce, wild, fast, to run, to flow; loud, noisy” and from “to run, to flow”, the meanings “water; body of water” developed: see PIE **mer-* meaning “sea, lake, wetland” and compare also PIE **móri*, “sea, standing water”.

From Proto-Indo-Iranian **mrgás* derives Sanskrit *mṛgá*, “wild beast; deer” and Proto-Iranian **mrgáh* “bird, hen”: the differing meanings come from the root-meaning that I posit: the “wild beast, deer” meaning developed as seen with Proto-Germanic **deur* (“wild) animal, beast”), which derives from PIE **deuzq*, “(wild) animal, beast”, in turn from PIE **d^hewsom*, in turn from PIE **d^hews/*d^hwes*=“to breathe (in or out); breath; spirit, soul > creature”, a root which I derive from a common word-initial **d^h*=“force” in PIE, and that word-initial **d^h*=“force” is encountered in many PIE roots, many of which I detail in the concluding section

of this paper. One of those roots is PIE **d^hew*, “to run” (from which derives Ancient Greek *θέω*=“I run (fast); I fly”).

From Proto-Germanic **deur* (“wild) animal, beast”) derives English *deer*, Old English *dēor* (“wild animal, beast”), Old High German *tior* (“animal”), and many more Germanic cognates.

Proto-Iranian **mrgáh* “bird, hen” (bird is the older meaning, hen is a later meaning) likely developed from the “spiritfull, lively, vigorous” semantics as well as the “to fly<run” semantic, but at the same time the word could have carried also the meaning “loud, noisy>singer”.

Germano-Celtic **márkos* (“horse”, “wild horse”) likely developed from the “fast, lively, vigorous, powerful” semantic, as seen in the etymology of English “horse”, deriving from PIE **k¹ers-* “to run”. How exactly **márkos* (“horse”, “wild horse”) is related to Proto-Indo-Iranian **mrgás* (as I believe they very likely are cognate) remains to be determined.

If my interpretation of **márkos* is correct, can **márkos* still be cognate to to Proto-Indo-Iranian **máryas* (“young man; stallion”)? Yes, they can be, via three different scenarios which I will detail in this paragraph. Whether **márkos* and **máryas* are cognates has been debated; I’m not sure whether they are cognate or not either. Proto-Indo-Iranian **máryas* (“young man; stallion”) derives from PIE **mér-yo-s*, a suffixed form of PIE **mer*=“young boy, girl”.

Scenario 1) a PIE **mer* meaning “wet” (from “to run”, in turn from “force”) could have led to “young, tender” as is often seen (ultimately from the fact that newborn mammals are wet, but also influenced by soft often moist young plant sprouts): if from “wet”, then this form of PIE **mer*=“young boy, girl” (from “wet”) would be cognate to PIE **mer* meaning “sea, lake, wetland”.

Scenario 2) If the meanings “young boy, girl” for **mer-* derive from “lively, vigorous” then again they would be cognate to **márkos* meaning “horse”/“wild horse”, if those horse meanings developed from “fast, lively, vigorous” as I posit.

Scenario 3) Alternatively, PIE **mer*=“young boy, girl” derives from the earlier meaning “a young shoot; a sprout”, in which case **márkos* meaning “horse”/“wild horse” could still be a cognate if the meanings “a shoot, a sprout” developed from **mer*=“to push out/to push up” in turn from “to push<force” (so it would not be necessary for the earlier meaning of **márkos* to have been “colt, juvenile horse, newborn horse”). But I have found no strong indications yet that PIE **mer*, -“young boy, girl” derives from “a young shoot; a sprout” rather than from “wet” or “lively, vigorous”.

Whether East Asian¹ **m()raŋ()* =”horse” is a cognate to Germano-Celtic **márkos* and/or to Proto-Indo-Iranian **mrgás* remains to be determined.

From Proto-Iranian **mrgáh* “bird, hen” developed words meaning “hen egg/chicken egg” (see Iranian Persian *morġāna*, Gilaki *moryāna*, etc.) as well as simply “egg” (see Mazanderani *mərġena*, “egg” and perhaps others).

An alternative scenario would be to derive **márkos* and **mrgás* from “pointed, sharp” leading to “fast” for **márkos*, while for **mrgás*: “horned; swift” (see the meanings of Ancient Greek *ὀξύς*: “sharp, pointed” but also “quick, swift”, among many more meanings) for the cervids and “fast” for the birds. It’s as yet unclear to me whether the meanings “pointed, sharp” are likely for **márkos* and **mrgás*, and unclear whether the meanings “pointed, sharp” could also derive from “force, power”: seems possible, since cutting and stabbing tools gave people powers and abilities they otherwise didn’t have, and those tools had the power to cut and pierce.

The fact that a number of horse words derive from “to flow>run” I believe explains why horses were sacred/under the dominion of Poseidon, Ancient Greek god of the sea/of the waters, and I believe that *Don/Dawon/Daon/Dan/Das* at the end of the various variants of Poseidon’s name derive from a root that meant “to run, set in motion”² (leading to “water; running water; body of water”) in turn from “force, strength: so the *Don/Dawon/Daon/Dan/Das* element at the end of the Greek sea-god’s (and also the god of fresh water springs and water in general) name implied not only “water” and “to run” but also “powerful, vigorous; fast; mighty” as well, hence Poseidon was also the god of earthquakes (earthquakes<force).

So Poseidon’s name meant more than just “Lord/Master of the Waters”. The *De/Da* in *Demeter/Damater* probably derives from “hard, firm” in turn from “force, strength” (note the Arcadian pairing of Poseidon as husband of Demeter): but possibly the meaning “to flow” was included as well, as possibly indicated by early Arcadian representations of Demeter as a mare/human hybrid with flowing snakes for hair and holding a dove in one hand (see Ancient Greek *θέω* = “I run (fast), I fly”) and a dolphin (creature of the flowing sea) in the other. The flowing mane of a horse, besides the speed of the horse, strengthened the connection of horses with flowing. The snakes of the Arcadian Demeter’s hair could also stand for “force; energy”.

PIE **h₁ék_{wos}* < **h₁ék_{us}* “stallion, horse” is already usually considered to derive from **h₁ék-*, “quick, swift”. Though similar to PIE **h₂ek-* “sharp”, the

1 Not all of East Asia: the form is reconstructed by Benedict (1972) from Proto-Mon-Khmer/Proto-Tibeto-Burman and Old Chinese forms.

2 As posited by Martin Nilsson and Michael Janda.

different laryngeal sound makes me think that PIE **h₁ék-*, “quick, swift” is more akin to PIE **h₁eh₁t-* “to breathe, breath” (but see also PIE **h₂enh₁*, “to breathe”, with the **h₂* sound at the beginning), PIE **h₁ésh₂r/*h₁ésh₂r_o=* “blood”, PIE **h₁eysh₂-* “to strengthen, propel”, PIE **h₁ers-*, “to flow”, **h₁es-* “to be” (which I derive from the earlier meanings “to breathe; breath; living”). PIE **h₁ésh₂r/*h₁ésh₂r_o=* “blood” is pretty surely a variation of PIE **h₁eysh₂-* “to strengthen, propel”.

I have an etymology for Ancient Greek Νηρέυς (Nereus) which is certain: Νηρέυς derives from Ner=“force, strong; mighty” encountered in Latin Nerius and Nero, which were traditionally described as meaning *fortis ac strenuus*, “strong and sturdy”. Etruscan “neri” meaning “water” derives from “to run” in turn from “force” so the Etruscan word is cognate to the Indo-European. The word was found in Proto-Indo-European as PIE **h₂nér*, “power, force, vital energy; man”.

Part 2

I posit that PIE **h₂éwis* (“bird”) meant “shrill, noisy; loud; singer”: this new interpretation I believe is indicated by a number of factors, including:

1) the strident harsh [**h₂*] sound at the beginning of the word: compare Ancient Greek χελιδών “the swallow bird” from PIE **g^hel-* “to cry out, shout, make noise”; and compare PIE **h₂énh₂ts / *h₂énh₂tis* “duck”.

2) the fact that in Albanian and Celtic, the only (? , I haven’t found others and I’ve looked well) words deriving from this root mean “duck”.

3) an [S] sound (which is often seen in onomatopoeic words indicating strident sounds) was prefixed to the **h₂* sound: see **(s)h₂wy-etó-s* > Proto-Celtic **(s)awyetos* “duck” and Proto-Albanian **sjāutā*, “duck”: the meaning “duck” and that prefixed [S] sound to me indicate “noisy”.

4) I have found that initial PIE **h₂* sometimes/often corresponds with initial K in various ancient Non-IE languages and sometimes within IE. And so I believe that the Ancient Greek word κῆβρος / κέϊπος / κῆπος, which referred to the long-tailed cercopithecus monkeys, referred to the loud, far-reaching and frequent calls of those cercopithecus monkeys, something that they are very known for. This would also be the etymology of Sanskrit kapi (monkey, ape, elephant: elephants are loud as well), Hebrew *qōf*, “ape” and Middle Persian *kabīg*, “monkey”. Likewise Proto-Germanic **apō* “ape, monkey” could derive from “noisy”, not from “a water-sprite”: I believe that PIE **h₂ep*, “water; body of water” comes from “loud; noisy” (the sounds of rushing and streaming water) as well as “force”, explaining also Latin *apis* (“bee”) as “noisy”: Latin *apis* is of unknown etymology, or was before my theory.

For PIE $*h_2ék^weh_2$, “water” I have found cross-correspondences among a number of PIE roots in IE which I will detail next time. The cross-correspondences support this conclusion: in PIE, word-initial $*h_2$ often has the same semantic values as PIE word-initial [St-] and [Kr-] (for PIE word-initial [St-] see my recent paper on that topic, the updated version of which will also discuss Kr- in detail). “Stream” and “strident” and “strix” (screech owl) and sturnus (“starling” a very harsh voiced bird) are some examples from a number where word-initial St= “a harsh, strident or rushing sound”: in the case of “stream” the sounds of rushing water. The word-initial Kr- has the same function in PIE $*kres$, “torrent, flood, surge, wave, fountain” (as I have determined), and I also posit that PIE $*krew^h_2$ - “blood outside the body” derives from “to rush out, stream out”, originally from Kr- denoting the sounds of rushing water.

And I conclude that in PIE $*h_2ék^weh_2$, “water”, $*h_2ék$ refers to the susurration/streaming sound of water, and in other cases this $*h_2$ would have referred to harsher, more strident, more shrill sounds (such as the cries of eagles, see Ancient Greek αἰετός/ἄετός) and also to non-harsh and not necessarily shrill but high-pitched vocalizations of various birds (see my theory about PIE $h_2éwis$ above).

And I posit that PIE $*h_2weh_1$ - “to blow (of the wind)” is an onomatopoeic word imitating the whistling/hissing/susurration of the wind, and is a root parallel to PIE $*sweysd$, “to hiss”, from which derives Welsh *chwythu*, “to blow”: the word is pronounced χωῶθι/χῶθι/hῶθι/hῶθι depending on the dialect.

This also indicates to me that PIE $*h_1ers$ - , “to flow” is a flowing word which derives from “breath; flowing air” not from the mimicking of the sounds of streaming water as I think is the case for $*h_2ék^weh_2$, “water”.

It’s also possible that PIE $*h_2éwis$ “bird” had the additional or primary meaning “fast” from “to run/force”, and so PIE $*h_2ék^weh_2$, “water” and PIE $*h_2ep$, “water” likely also referred to the running of the water and the strength of some running water/flowing water/bodies of water/tides/surf/floods.

Part 3.

Ancient Greek οἰωνός = “large bird, bird of prey” (οἰωνός < $*h_2ow-i-ō(n)$ according to Beekes, 2010) indicates to me that in PIE $*h_2ow$ meant “bulky, rounded, fat, a larger mass” and even sometimes “powerful”, with that meaning deriving from “big, fat, bulky”.

PIE $*h_2ówis$ (“sheep”) I posit derives from the earlier meaning “fat, burgeoning” (compare οἰωνός, “large bird of prey” < $*h_2ow-i-ō(n)$) and PIE $*h_1ówHd^hr_$ = “udder” (but this “udder” root has $*h_1$ not $*h_2$).

But what was the source of this PIE form **h₂ów/*h₂ow-* meaning “swollen, fat, bulky” even sometimes “powerful”? It was not a root meaning “to blow out; swell” and instead the root had to do with “thickening, hardening, mass, bulk, rounded”.

The **h₂ów/*h₂ow-* forms under discussion here quite surely correspond in an as-yet undetermined way with a word whose semantics fit perfectly and a word which is of unknown etymology and origin: English “cob” believe it or not (see this note³ for other instances where word-initial PIE **h₂* corresponds to K in another language, in forms attested well after PIE). I will not describe all the meanings of English “cob” here, instead I will note the highlights:

Cob: 1) A horse having a stout body and short legs

2) the big bulky Black-backed gull, *Larus marinus*

3) A round often crusty roll or loaf of bread

4) One who is eminent, great, large or rich

5) a large fish, especially the fat/plump cod fish

6) A spider (a reference to the plump, round/rounded abdomens

of spiders)

7) A tower or small castle on top of a hill

8) A building material consisting of clay, sand, straw, water and earth, similar to adobe

9) male swan

10) gang leader, bully (these meanings attested in Middle English, with the spelling “cobbe”

11) A lump or piece of anything, usually of a somewhat large size, as of coal, or stone.

All these meanings I posit come from “a thick(ened) fat mass”, “a bulk, often rounded”, “a conglomeration/congregation of material into something thick, bulky”: and I have a certainty (after studying this for some time) that that is the origin of PIE **h₂ówis*, as well as of Ancient Greek οἰωνός, “large bird of prey” (<PIE **h₂ow-i-ō(n)*) and of PIE **h₂ōwyóm*, “egg”.

Icelandic *kobbi*, “seal, pinniped” I believe is cognate to English “cob/cobb/cobbe” and has the etymology I described in the paragraph above, and so does not derive from PIE **gew*, “to bend, curve, arch, vault”, a wrong old derivation found in Pokorny’s IEW.

The earlier meaning “fat plump thickened mass” that I posit for “sheep” is quite likely. And sheep among the Proto-Indo-Europeans were surely directly linked with the ancient fat fertility goddesses of abundance, which is likely since

³ Compare Arabic *kabš*, “ram, bellwether”; Phoenician *kbš*, “sheep”; Akkadian *kabsu*, “young male sheep”; Classical Syriac *keḇšā*, “wether”, Hebrew *kébeš*, “sheep”.

sheep-herding was probably the main type of livestock herding of the Proto-Indo-Europeans.

So semantically my proposal is very likely, and semantically there is no need for **h₂ówis* to have referred to the wool, nor to shearing the wool, nor to “clothed”, nor a meaning of “the one that produces clothing (from wool)”, as Pooth suggested⁴, nor to “curly” (referring to the wool), nor to bleating, nor to milk, nor to “white”; nor do I think that **h₂ówis* meant “food”, which would be referring to the milk and to the meat of the sheep.

I will now detail a root-word for “calf” in Germanic which makes my etymology of **h₂ówis* more likely.

The Proto-Germanic word **kalbaz* meant “calf”. Someone at some point posited that **kalbaz* derives from PIE **g^welb^h-* “womb”, comparing Avestan *gərəbuš*, “young animal”. But as Kroonen (et al.?) points out, an etymology deriving **kalbaz* from PIE **g^welb^h-* is problematic due to the missing labiovelar in Germanic⁵. Instead, I agree in essence (if not necessarily exactly, given an alternative possibility which I will describe in this paragraph) with Pokorny’s etymology of **kalbaz* which derives it from PIE **gel(e)b^(h)-* as a labial expression of PIE **gel-* “form into a ball; ball”. As a close cognate, Pokorny cited Latin *galba* which meant “a small worm, the ash-borer, or the larva of the ash-spinner, *Bombyx aesculi*,”⁶ while in Gaul among the Gauls, *galba* meant “fat paunch, big belly”, or as others have it, “a stout⁷fat person”. As Pokorny believed, those meanings of *galba* probably come from “rounded, fat” in turn from PIE **gel-* “form into a ball; ball”. However irregular sound correspondences between **kalbaz* and *galba* might point to substrate origin: but if so, I think it would be a substrate word that had either the same meaning as PIE **gel-* “form into a ball; ball” or a similar

4 See pages 29-30 of Pooth, Roland A. *Proto-Indo-European Nominal Morphology. Part 1: The Noun*. 2015. The PIE root he points to is PIE **h₂eu(H)-* “dress, be dressed, clothe oneself”, he cites LIV, page 275: **h₂eu(H)-*. I derive the “dress, be dressed, clothe oneself, deck something” meanings from “to add a padding onto something, a covering; to bulk oneself up with coverings/clothing”, in turn from “a thickened congelation/obscuration”, and so it is a variation of the meaning found in the similar **h₂ów/*h₂ow* form. But I see no reason to think that the sheep word meant “covered (with wool)” when the meanings of English *cob/cobb/cobbe* and Icelandic/Old Norse *kobbi* suggest a scenario which I think is so much more likely.

5 Kroonen, Guus (2013), “**kalbiz-*”, in *Etymological Dictionary of Proto-Germanic* (Leiden Indo-European Etymological Dictionary Series; 11), Leiden, Boston: Brill, p. 278.

6 A Latin Dictionary. Founded on Andrews' edition of Freund's Latin dictionary. revised, enlarged, and in great part rewritten by Charlton T. Lewis, Ph.D. and Charles Short, LL.D. Oxford. Clarendon Press. 1879.

7 Here “stout” is to be understood as “thick, stocky, plump”.

meaning: “to bulge, plump, pudgy”. The irregular sound correspondences can be due to borrowings from unknown IE languages which are now lost, and if so then source can be PIE *gel-”form into a ball; ball”, with irregularities due to the fact that it was a loanword from a different IE language. In summary, Proto-Germanic *kalbaz (“calf”) most likely does not derive from PIE *g^welb^h-⁸, and instead likely derives from the meaning “fat, plump, pudgy”. The Mingrelian word ქაბლა (kabila=“heifer, calf”; the word is attested with several variants) is likely not cognate to *kalbaz, but does likely come from a Near Eastern/Middle Eastern root that had the same meaning, since the Mingrelian and Semitic forms (Arabic *kabš*, “ram, bellwether”; Phoenician *kbš*, “sheep”; Akkadian *kabsu*, “young male sheep”; Classical Syriac *keḅšā*, “wether”⁹, Hebrew *kébeś*, “sheep”) are so close to the well-known Semitic root *k-b-r*=“big, large, great”.

PIE **h*₂*ōwyóm* (“egg”): my theory (due to the nearly identical form of the **h*₂*ów-* in **h*₂*ówis* and the **h*₂*ōw-* in **h*₂*ōwyóm*) is that the meaning of the **h*₂*ōw* in **h*₂*ōwyóm* was very close to the meaning of **h*₂*ów-* in **h*₂*ówis*. My primary theory is that the **h*₂*ōw* in **h*₂*ōwyóm* originally meant “rounded mass” and that **h*₂*ōw* is parallel but not necessarily cognate to English “cob/cobb/cobbe”. Furthermore my explanation captures the essence of what an egg is better than “that which is in the nest”, a meaning which I have seen more than two people posit over the years.

Considering the meaning “small castle on top of a hill” seen for “cob”, it’s just possible that **h*₂*ōwyóm* literally meant the “home/structure/cabin” of the unhatched creature, but that’s not so likely.

PIE **h*₂*ewg-*, **h*₂*weg-* “to increase, to enlarge” is most likely a root cognate to **h*₂*ōw*. And also PIE **h*₂*welh*₁, “to rule; strong, powerful”.

Part 4

I have more than one theory to account for the origin of PIE **h*₂*ew-* “to see, perceive; appear; manifest, obvious, clear”: the one I think is most likely is that those meanings come from “to condense, thicken; firm”, leading to “something clearly seen, clearly visible; to make out things easily because they are defined and substantial”: I think this is the most likely because I find no explicit unambiguous

8 If an unknown/unattested variant (which could be from a substrate language) of **g^welb^h* existed and if that variant was one that would fit **kalbaz*, then that would be a likely source. But there is no evidence of such a root: **kalbaz* on its own does not constitute evidence of such a root.

9 A wether can be a castrated ram or a castrated goat. The “castrated” meaning, judging from the meanings of the cognates (“sheep; young male sheep”), was a semantic shift that came later.

evidence of the meanings “light, bright” in PIE $*h_2ew-$: the best indication of those meanings would be PIE $*h_2ews$, “dawn, east”, but I have a likely derivation of the “dawn” meaning from “to rise” or “to grow” (see that discussion later in this work).

So I no longer favor my earlier theory that this $*h_2ew-$ root derives from the meanings “bright” and “sharp”¹⁰. I also have some other theories about this root which can be read in this note: ¹¹.

There is another PIE $*h_2ew-$ root which is the source of Latin *aveo* and *avidus* : based on a number of factors, including the determination of some scholars of Latin that Lucretius’ use of *avidus* and *aveo as* “large, abundant” conveys clearly one of the prime root-meanings of this particular $*h_2ew-$ root, I posit that this root meant “big, large, immense, vast, intense; powerful”, from a hypothetical PIE/Pre-PIE $**h_2e=$ “force, strong, hard, thick, dense, large, intense”. The other factors I base this on include the parallel example of the Latin word *vastus* which can mean “immense, enormous, prodigious, vast” as well as “insatiable” (“insatiable” and “voracious” are two meanings of *avidus* as well). The meanings of the Sanskrit cognate *avati* indicate this interpretation as well, though the “guard, defend” meanings of *avati* may, as has already been posited, derive from PIE $*h_1ewH$, “to help, assist, protect”.

PIE $*h_2ewló$, “something hollow, hollowed out” likely derives from “scooped out/hollowed out by something sharp/pointed” (if not from $*h_2ewló$ being an imitation of the sound of air blowing through a hollow tube), which is the usual origin for such words. So then we have $*h_2ew[**]=$ “sharp”, as I posited above, with “sharp” paired with “bright”: but of course in the root $*h_2ewló$ only

10 think of a well-lit scene where things are seen clearly and well-defined, so “sharp” and “bright” as opposed to “blurry” and “dim”. The earlier meanings “bright, sharp” would derive from the harsh scraping sound of [$*h_2$] being directly associated with “harsh, hard, sharp, bright, shrill, loud”, as seen with the meanings of Ancient Greek $ὀξύς$: “sharp, harsh, shrill, dazzling, bright etc.”

11 Other theories that I have for the origin of PIE $*h_2ew-$ “to see, perceive; appear; manifest, obvious, clear” is that it derives from “to use power, force, ability”, from a hypothetical Pre-PIE $**h_2e=$ “force, strong, hard, thick, dense”. I don’t think that this $*h_2ew-$ derives from “to grasp”, as I think PIE $*derk-$, “to see” derives from “to grasp” in which case $*derk-$ would be a variant of PIE $*dʰerǵʰ$, “to bind fast, be firm” and PIE $*dʰer$, “to hold fast”. But PIE $*h_2ew-$ “to see, perceive; appear; manifest, obvious, clear” may derive from “to cut” leading to “to discern” (and I think PIE $*spek-$ “to see, to look, to observe” derives from “to cut>to discern”, a derivation that I believe is indicated by a number of things, including that in the Hellenic branch the root was metathesized to $*skép-$), in turn leading to “to see, perceive, hear, manifest, obvious” and the other meanings. That there likely was a $*h_2ew$ meaning “sharp” in Pre-PIE is likely indicated by the PIE root $*h_2ewló$, “something hollow, hollowed out” unless that root derives from the imitation of the sound of air blowing through a hollow tube, which is actually quite likely as well.

the meaning “something hollow, hollowed out” was retained/employed. Ancient Greek *καυλός* (“stem, stalk, shaft”) shows the {**h₂/k*} variation again. Proto-Balto-Slavic **káu²las*, “bone”.

PIE **h₂ewH-*¹² (also reconstructed as **h₃ew-*¹³, **h₁eu-*¹⁴, and **eu-*¹⁵) which is the root described by LIV as meaning “to put on clothes or shoes”, I think derives (as described in a note earlier) from “to add a padding onto something, a covering; to bulk oneself up with coverings/clothing”, in turn from “a thickened congelation/obscuration”, and so it is a variation of the meaning found in the similar **h₂ów/*h₂ow* form and I expect the root to begin with **h₂* or **h₃*, but not **h₁* or **e*. From this **h₂ewH-* root derives Hittite: *unu-*, “to adorn; decorate; lay/set a table”; Tocharian *ewe*=”skin, hide”; Avestan *aθra*, “shoe” et al.

There is also the more well-known PIE **wes-* “to dress, clothe” which is perhaps a variant: but if a variant **wes-* would have to have the same kind of origin as I described for **h₂ewH-*. Another scenario is that they do both have the same semantic origin but they are not variants just parallel roots. In a future edition I will see what new details I can find out about this **wes*.

PIE **h₂wes-* “to dwell, live, reside; to stay, to spend the night”: looking these meanings as well as some other meanings deriving from this root, the root-meaning was “firm, stiff, staying in place, strong, pith, core, essence”. It’s actually quite clear. It is therefore similar to PIE **h₂welh₁*, “strong, powerful, to rule”.

PIE **h₂éwh₂os*, **h₂éwh₂s* ~ **h₂uh₂ós*, *h₂éwh₂ō* =”maternal grandfather”, is very likely from the same semantic shift seen in Proto-Balto-Slavic **stā²ras* “old”, which is known to derive from the older meanings “big, thick; that which has accrued” seen in Lithuanian *stóras*, “thick, fat”, and Old Norse *stórr*, “big, tall, large, great”, which would be from older “thick, fat”.

PIE **h₂yew-* “straight, upright” comes from **h₂y*=”stiff, firm, erect”, from PIE **h₂ey-* “vital force, life, age, eternity”---e.g., “that which remains firm, stable” and also “stability, firmness, strength”.

There also is said to be a PIE **h₂ey-*, “day, morning”---morning suggests “rising” which suggests “straight, upright”. PIE **h₂ews*, “dawn, east” might derive from the earlier meanings “bright, light”, possibly from earlier **h₂e*=”harsh, sharp”, seen also in PIE **h₂ek-*, “sharp”, and possibly (compare PIE **lewk*=”bright; light; to shine; to see”) in PIE **h₂ew*, “to see, perceive; manifest, evident, clear, obvious”, which may also be from “sharp, bright”.

12 Rix, Helmut, editor (2001), “**h₂euH-*”, in LIV [*Lexicon of Indo-European Verbs*] (in German), 2nd edition, Wiesbaden: Dr. Ludwig Reichert Verlag.

13 Derksen, Rick (2015) *Etymological Dictionary of the Baltic Inherited Lexicon* (Leiden Indo-European Etymological Dictionary Series; 13), Leiden, Boston: Brill, page 73.

14 Adams, Douglas Q. (2013), “*ewe*”, in *A Dictionary of Tocharian B: Revised and Greatly Enlarged* (Leiden Studies in Indo-European; 10), Amsterdam, New York: Rodopi.

15 Pokorny, Julius (1959), *IEW*. Volume 1, p. 346.

However, PIE **h₂ews*, “dawn, east” likely instead derives from the earlier meaning “rising” in turn from “erect” in turn from “erect, stiff, firm”, from “firm, stiff, hard, thick, dense”. It likely had a counterpart beginning with the K- sound in some ancient language (s), a counterpart that could have had the form(s) *Keb/Kebs*, which would be similar to PIE **kab-*, “firm, strong, dense; erect; stiff”.

Burushaski/Burusho *kabut* (“white horse”) I believe shows that the meanings “bright, light, white” could have been intertwined with the meanings that I specify in the paragraph above this one. One can imagine an ancient root **h₂e(w/v/b)/*ke(w/v/b)* = “harsh, sharp, hard, bright”; without the w/v/b, the root is seen also in PIE **h₂ek-*, “sharp”.

I expect that PIE **h₁ews-*, “to burn” is unrelated to PIE **h₂ews*, “dawn, east”, but there is also PIE **h₂eHs-* / **h₂es-* / **h₂eh₁s-* “to burn, to glow; to be dry; to dry; hearth; ashes”, so there could, in addition to what I specified earlier, be some idea of “flaming, burning” in PIE **h₂ews*, “dawn, east”.

My theory about the origin of PIE **h₁ews-*, “to burn” and PIE **h₂eHs-* / **h₂es-* / **h₂eh₁s-*: “to burn, to glow; to be dry; to dry; hearth; ashes”: the **h₁* sound denoted “hot breath”, because expelling hot breath and making the h₁ sound (similar to the H in English Hat) sound are so close to each other (and this explains all the **Heh-* / **Hews-* type of roots referring to “hot, warm, burning”).

**h₂* was a harsh scraping laryngeal sound. The **h₁* sound was more suited for (or in any case it was the one used for) the “expelling hot breath” semantic, which led to “hot; warm; to burn”.

PIE **h₁er-* “earth” may derive from “firm, hard, strong” or “supporting”, with “supporting” deriving from “firm, strong”, and “firm, strong” deriving from “full of breath/full of life-force”: I compare PIE **h₁er-* “earth” to PIE **d^her-* “to hold; hold fast; support”, and so I do not think that **h₁er-* “earth” derives from “dry”¹⁶. Besides “firm, hard, strong” the meaning “erect, elevated” may also have been included, as seen with Ancient Greek *χέρσος* “dry land” from PIE **ǵ^hers-* “stand erect; stiff; bristle”. “Erect” in this case of PIE **h₁er-* would have derived from “full of life-force”, inspired by the hardening and rising of the penis.

PIE **h₂erh₃-* “to plough” likely derives from “hard plough” referring to the material that ploughs are made of, or to “strengthening, making (the soil) productive”: both options are from “hard, firm, strong”.

I posit that PIE **h₂ek-* “sharp”, PIE **h₂eyk-* “sharp/pointed”, PIE **h₂eng^h-* / **h₂emǵ^h*, “tight, narrow; to compress, press”, PIE **h₂eyǵ-* (“oak; goat”)¹⁷ all ultimately derive from “firm, strong” leading on the one hand to “tight,

16 Aurelius Quidam has posited that PIE **h₁er-* “earth” derives from the meaning “dry”.

17 PIE **h₁eyǵ-* / **h₁yeg-* / **yeg* (= “ice, frost”) probably derive from “congealed”, from “thickened”, from “thick, strong” (with “strong” referring also the to power of cold, probably) from “full of life-force”, from

narrow; to compress, press” and on the other to “pointed, sharp”(see my other works for how the “goat” meaning derives from “pointed, projecting”: it’s a reference to the penis and horns of the goat, the lasciviousness of the male goats: see the etymology of English “stag” for a similar semantic development) because if something is soft, it can’t cut, and something that can cut has power, and had virtue for ancient peoples. The ultimate origin for these **h₂* words is the harsh sound of **h₂* leading to the meanings “hard, firm, stiff, erect, sharp” and so on. PIE **h₂eǵ-* “to drive; impel” would be from “force; firm; hard” and PIE **h₂eǵ^h-*, “cow” would be from “thick, fat, big”, with “thick” being the older meaning, from “hard, firm”.

At the same time they may also contain the “full of life-force/breath<breath, to breathe” semantics found for sure in many **h₁* words, explaining PIE **h₁ers-*, “to flow”, **h₁es-* “to be” (which I derive from the earlier meanings “to breathe; breath; living”), PIE **h₁eh₁t-* “to breathe, breath”, PIE **h₂enh₁*, “to breathe”, PIE **h₁ésh₂r/*h₁ésh₂r_o=* “blood”, and most of the PIE roots beginning with **h₁/*h₂/*h₃*: PIE **h₁eǵ-* “to say”, from “breath; life”

Word-initial **h₃* laryngeal may also have had such meanings in PIE in some words: see PIE **h₃ep-*, “ability; force; to work, toil, make”.

For my etymology of PIE **h₁er-* “earth”, compare my etymology for PIE **h₁r-i-(e)t-/*h₁er-* “certain domestic animal”, which I derive from “breath; living creature; vigorous, fertile, productive” (and see also the PIE adjective **h₁wésus* = “good, excellent”, which probably derives from “vigour, liveliness” as Pooth indicates¹⁸). And PIE **h₁er-* “earth” likely also included the meanings “fertile, productive, full of life-force”. Phrygian “eroka” with the variant “oroka”, hypothesized by Lubotsky to mean “progeny, offspring”, surely derive from this set of roots that I am detailing.

PIE **h₃er-* “to move, to stir, to rise, to spring; to quarrel, fight” may derive from this set as well. And Ancient Greek *Ἥρα* (Hera) may have meant “full of life-force; productive” if not “bright, radiant” as I theorized before: and Ancient Greek *Ἥρω* (=Hero) may have meant “full of life-force; productive; mighty” if not “bright, radiant” as I theorized before.

The PIE root **h₁yaǵ-/*h₁yeh₂ǵ-*, **Hyaǵ-*, **yaǵ-*, **yaǵ-*, **yeh₂ǵ-*, often defined as “to worship, sacrifice” I posit is derived from “to bind, make a compact with (a compact with spirits/gods), to bind an offering to, to solidify a relationship with gods/spirits”, and from there in Luwian we find the meanings “to make, perform” (but not “to do” apparently) and in Tocharian B *yānk-* the meanings “to

“breath/to flow”. Same origin for PIE **h₁eyH-* “ice, frost”.

18 For PIE **h₁wésus* (“good, excellent”) deriving from “vigour, liveliness”, see page 34 column 2 of Pooth’s *Proto-Indo-European Nominal Morphology. Part 1: The Noun*. 2015.

cast a spell, bewitch; to delude (the meaning “to delude” came from “a binding spell cast on someone, so a bewitchment deluding them/making them hallucinate, etc”). I think the Luwian “to make” meaning from this root comes from this same idea to “solidify” something; such rites in time became thought of as “to worship” to use an English word. So the “ice, frost” words are cognate to this “to bind, make a compact, solidify a relationship with gods/spirits” (Pre-PIE meanings), both from “to harden, congeal”. That’s also why those “ice, frost” words (**h₁eyg-/*h₁eyǵ-*, **h₁yeg-/*h₁yeǵ-*, **yeg/yeǵ-*) and this root (**h₁yaǵ-/*h₁yeh₂ǵ-*, **Hyaǵ-*, **yaǵ-*, **yaǵ-*, **yeh₂ǵ-*) are so close in form: the “ice, frost” words are (I posit) from “to harden, congeal”, as is so often the case for “ice, frost” words.

PIE **yewg-* “to yoke, join, tie together” would be a kindred root to what I described in the comment above, those meanings of **yewg-* deriving from the earlier meaning “tight, dense, compacted”, like a bunch of sticks tied together tight as opposed to a loose pile of sticks. The likely vacillation with laryngeal or not in those two roots (“to worship, sacrifice” and “ice, frost”) comes from two sets of roots (the ones beginning with a laryngeal and denoting “firm, strong, tight” and the ones beginning with Y and denoting the same) being linked, creating a spectrum, and a situation parallel to the “S-mobile” which is really a St/T and Sk/k and Sp/p (etc.) vacillation going back to very kindred roots.

In Sumerian, after publishing my theory, I have found some very interesting possible corroboration of my theory: compare Sumerian *šeg*, “a deer or mountain goat” (<hard, stiff erect horns, phallic, vigorous, strong, horny) ; Sumerian *šeg*, “snow; sleet; cold weather; frost, ice” (<to harden, to congeal, probably); Sumerian *še/šeg* - “to agree, to be in agreement”, which may come from “a pact, compact” in turn from “firm, thick, dense, hard”, see for example the etymology of “pact”; Sumerian *šeg*, “mudbrick, brick”; Sumerian *še* = “barley”, which could be from *še* = “stiff pointed bristles” as well as “erect, sprouting up”, both from “hard, stiff>erect”.

PIE **yewh₁/*yew* “to ripen, mature, grow” most likely comes from “rising up” from “erect, stiff, hard”, so that this root is cognate to PIE **yewg*, “to yoke, join, tie together” (similar to “agreement” in Sumerian), which I posit is from “firm, thick, dense, compact, hard”. PIE **yewos*, “barley, spelt, cereal, grain” derives from **yewh₁/*yew* as already realized.

Because of the h/k variation in its variants, Basque *habia* (“nest”) likely derives from an earlier $*h_2$. Is the word from “hollow<sharp, pointed” and so akin to PIE $*h_2ewló$? Or is it from the meanings “to settle; to live; place where one settles; habitation; home” from “staying in place, firm, hard”, and akin to PIE $*h_2wes-$ “to dwell, live, reside; to stay, to spend the night”?

Basque *habia*¹⁹ has the variants *abia*, *kabia*, *kafia*, *abira*, *abi*, *kabi*, *api*, *aapi*: I don’t think that the K was necessarily prothetic, it may be from old variant roots: some with $*h_2$, some with K.

Habia is also found as an element in Basque and Basque-area river-names: two examples are *Uhabia* (a coastal river of the French Basque country) and *Ardanabia*, a left tributary of the Adour, a river in southwestern France. See also *Azkabi*, *Habiaga*, *Zehabia*, *Zehabiaga*, *Intzabi*, *Okabe*. It has already been proposed that this is cognate to the “nest” word, and a work by Lhande from 1926 posited the root-meaning “hole, lower place”²⁰ and similarly Mitxelena over 50 years posited that Basque *habia* derives from Latin *cavea*.

I disagree with Lhande and Mitxelena: I posit that the root-meaning was “to flow” from a harsh laryngeal, probably $*h_2$ that imitated the sounds of rushing water (an earlier version of this work suggested that the river-element *Habia* might derive from “place to settle and live”, since rivers were preferred for making settlements/villages, towns/cities).

The “nest” and “beehive” words come from “home (of birds/bees)”, from “firm, staying in place”, but they may also derive from “hollow”. The beehive words are Basque *abe* and *kabe* and there’s also Biscayan *abao/abau* (“honeycomb”) and Bearnese *càben* ‘beehive’: if the root-meaning was “home, habitation” then Late Latin *cabanna* (of unknown origin and unknown etymology; source of English “cabin”) meaning “hut” is a cognate.

Latin *apis/apēs* (“bee”) is of unknown etymology and has been proposed to be a substrate word: I think it is a substrate word and I posit that it is cognate to Basque *abia/habia*, and that the root-meaning of *apis* was “of the bee-hive”, from $*apia$ =beehive. Or instead I posit that *apis/apēs* (“bee”) may be from $*h_2e$ used to imitate the sounds of rushing, flowing, buzzing, and the flowing of honey in a beehive was probably also referenced. I have not seen anyone deriving the Basque beehive words from Latin *apiarium* (=the area reserved for beekeeping purposes, contrasted with the hive itself, which was called *alveare/alvearium*) and I think that, since the Latin word is of unknown etymology, more likely the Latin

19 Basque *habia* has the variants *abia*, *kabia*, *kafia*, *abira*, *abi*, *kabi*, *api*, *aapi*. *abira* shows an added -ra suffix (*abi*>*abira*), or an R added epentically between the I and A vowel sounds: *abia*>*abira*.

20 Lhande, P. *Dictionnaire Basque-Français et Français-Basque*, 1926.

apis/apes derive from a substrate language, and the hydronyms in Basque (which are likely cognate) indicate a native source.

I have not seen anyone positing that the Basque hydronym elements derive from PIE **h₂ep*="body of water". PIE **h₂ep* is likely a cognate deriving from a word used to imitate the sound of rushing water.

Part 6

PIE **(s)teg-* "to cover, hide, obscure" I posit comes from "a thickening, hardening, stiffening obscuration", from St/T="stiff, hard, harsh". PIE **kel*, "to cover" I post also comes from "a thickening, hardening, stiffened obscuration" and Ancient Greek *κρύπτω* (variant *κρύφω*) also comes from Kr="to stiffen, harden, congeal" (the same Kr- that denotes harsh, strident sounds in PIE/IE and the sounds of rushing water in PIE **kres*, "torrent, surge, wave, fountain"), kindred to Ancient Greek *kruos* "ice, frost", Proto-Slavic **kryti* "to cover, to hide" et al. such as Latvian *kraut* "to pile, to stack" and Proto-Germanic **hraukaz* "pile (of stones), heap" (see PIE **krewH-* "to heap up"). From the original meaning these roots could also later/soon apply to clouds covering the sky: clouds are thickened congelations of water.

Ancient Greek *σταφυλή/σταφυλίζ* (ripe fresh grapes, bunch of grapes) is most likely from *staph*="trunk of the grape-vine", from PIE **steb^h-*, "post, stem"²¹. Compare Galician *cepa*="trunk of a vine and the vine itself", with *cepa* deriving from Latin *cippus*="post". This etymology is proven by the additional meaning: *staphule/staphulis*: "a plumb-bob/pumb-bob level/plummet", used to measure the height, having to do with "standing upright, vertical", as a check of an encyclopedia or dictionary will show. Hence from the plumb-bob, the adjective "plumb" meaning "truly vertical" developed, as well as the noun "aplomb" in French originally meaning "uprightness>stability>equilibrium>poise".

Part 7

Ancient Greek *γῆ, γᾶ, γαῖα* ("earth") I posit derives from the meanings "hard, firm, thick, dense" and I think those forms are likely cognate with Basque *ke*="smoke", which is likely from "thick, dense" as well.

21 I have been aware of this etymology (which was thought of decades ago, I assume) for quite a number of years, but for some reason I wasn't convinced: the Galician "cepa" example convinces me.

I also posit that PIE **geh₂w-*“to rejoice” and PIE **geh₂d^h-*“to rejoice” are likely from “full, fat, satiated, happy”, with “full, fat” deriving from earlier “thick, dense, firm”²².

Ancient Greek *γη-πάτταλος* means “oblong radish”: *πάτταλος*= “oblong” as indicated by *πάσσᾶλος/ πάτταλος* = “membrum virile” and “peg on which to hang clothes” (Beekes considers *πάσσᾶλος/ πάτταλος* to be Pre-Greek, only coincidentally similar to PIE **reh₂ǵ-* “to attach, fix, fasten; pole”).

The *γη* in *γη-πάτταλος* may mean “earth”, so that *γη-πάτταλος*= “earth-peg/earth-penis”: but I think instead that here *γη*= “radish”, from *γη*= “compacted into a ball” in turn from “firm, thick, dense”. An alternative scenario is that the *γη* in *γη-πάτταλος* means “root”, from earlier “that which is fixed firm”, from “firm, strong, hard, supporting”, possibly also including “erect, stiff, projecting”. The meanings “firm, strong, hard, supporting” and “covering (the meaning “covering” coming from “a thickened congelation”)” would have given rise to *γῆ, γᾶ, γαῖᾶ* = “earth”²³.

I derive Ancient Greek *κῆτος* (“whale; sea-monster”) from the earlier meaning “thick, dense, hard, firm” leading to “fat, big, massive”, and I derive *κήτημα*= “salted tuna fish” from there as well, because tuna are big fish. The word is cognate to Ancient Greek *γάδος*= “cod fish” and to Koine Greek *γάδαρος* (first attested 2nd century CE)/*γαϊδάριον/γαείδαρος*= “donkey” (compare how Ancient Greek *ὄνος* referred to donkeys/asses as well as to fish of the cod family): the application donkeys/asses arises from “fat, thick, firm, strong” leading to “strong/firm/supporting”, referring to how donkeys/asses carry heavy loads.

I derive Ancient Greek *γήθῦον/ γήτειον/ κητίον* (“a kind of onion”, which I found out referred to the pearl onion, a type of smaller, rounder, whiter, sweeter onions that look like big pearls) from “compacted into a ball” in turn from “dense, thick, firm”. Likewise, Ancient Greek *ὄνος* meant “donkey, ass (the equine),

22 My previous theory was that PIE **geh₂w-*“to rejoice” and PIE **geh₂d^h-*“to rejoice” are from “to swell; bloom; brighten”>“to be glad, to rejoice, be triumphant; take pride in” (compare how Ancient Greek *γάνος* means “brightness, sheen; gladness, joy, pride”, and I recall some other examples like this in various languages).

23 My first idea years ago was in fact that *γῆ, γᾶ, γαῖᾶ* derives from “firm, thick, dense, hard”, so what I wrote in the previous version of this, that my “original theory” was that *γῆ, γᾶ, γαῖᾶ* came from “breath; life-force; flowing”: that statement was not accurate. That statement disregarded my ideas about the etymology that I had from long before I was writing about that etymology in my recent papers. In recent notebook entries, I theorized that *γήθῦον/ γήτειον/ κητίον* (“a kind of onion”, which I found out referred to the pearl onion, a type of smaller, rounder, whiter, sweeter onions that look like big pearls), and I derive from **Ge(t)*= “to blow; swell; bloom; bright; white” (compare PIE **b^hel-* “to blow; swell up” and PIE **b^hel-*, “white”; and there are many more examples in human languages showing that semantic pairing). In a later entry I derived those onions words (*γήθῦον/ γήτειον/ κητίον* and the *γη* (radish?) of *γη-πάτταλος*) from the meaning “root”, from “planted in firm, holding fast<firm, strong, dense”. I prefer my theory that the source meaning for the onion and radish words was “compacted into firm ball”<“firm, strong, dense”.

woodlouse/pill-bug” and some other meanings not necessary to discuss in this paper; I posit that On in ὄνος=“firm, dense, thick, strong”, so referencing the ability of those equines to carry heavy loads, and the application to the woodlouse/pill-bug (the only completely terrestrial crustacean on earth these days) I think comes not so much from the hard shell but instead mostly from the way the pill-bug rolls up into a compact ball.

Ancient Greek γηθέω/γαθέω/γάθω/γήθω (=“to rejoice, be glad; to exult, triumph”) probably derive from “fat; satiated”. The meanings of Ancient Greek γάνος=“brightness, sheen; gladness, joy, pride” I derive from “fat; satiated”: compare the PIE pair *b^hel-, “white” and *b^hel-, “to swell”. Likewise for the Ancient Greek stem γαν=“fat, white” in Ancient Greek, a connection at least in part derived from the round (fat) white-yellow usually mood-uplifting sun.

See Ancient Greek γανῖται=“glutton”, clearly from Gan=“swollen, fat” (compare Latin *gumia*=“glutton”, cognate with Ancient Greek γέμω=“to be full”), and see how γάνδομα and γάδος (from Gad=“fat, thick” I think, I will work more on this “white” meaning for Gad- next time: should be the same explanation as for Gan-) according to Hesychius of Alexandria both refer to “white wheat meal” and to “wheat”; and γανδάω=“to shine”. So when I derive PIE *geh₂w-“to rejoice” and PIE *geh₂d^h-“to rejoice”, via the semantic shift “thick, fat>to swell>bloom; brighten” leading to “to be glad, to rejoice, be triumphant; take pride in”---that is extremely likely. And the older base form of the root was likely *geh₂, without the w/d^h seen in the two derivative roots. A root *geh₂ that meant “thick, fat>to swell; bloom; brighten”.

For “firm, strong, supporting” compare Gaia to the Gai- in γαῖδάριον/γαείδαρος=“donkey”. Compare also the similarity of the Latin names Gaius/Gaia (from PIE *geh₂w-“to rejoice” probably going back to “fat”) to Ancient Greek Gaia=“Earth”. And compare Ancient Greek γαίω (γαῖω)=“to rejoice, exult, take pride in”, from PIE *geh₂w-“to rejoice”. The Latin name Caesar may be from this same source. In antiquity, there was talk of a Punic word for “elephant” which was similar to Caesar: that may be cognate as well, referring to “big, fat, thick, strong, swollen”.

The ethnic term Γέτης (plural Getai=the Getae) likely meant “strong, thick, firm” and maybe also “vigorous, blooming”: on an old map based on ancient Roman sources, the Getae are called Gaete: likely because some Romans who made the map knew what Getae meant, that it was akin to the name Gaius (and maybe the variant form Gaete is a variant from the Daco-Getans and attested only on that map). My work on the etymology of the ethnonym Daci/Dacus suggests that it had the same meaning that I attribute to Getae. See Albanian Dak=“big

ram”, from PIE **d^heu*, “force, life-force>breath, to breathe, be alive, in power; living creature; vigorous, powerful, fierce”.

I expect that the Geb- of Gebeleixis comes from a root that had the oldest meanings “hard; sharp; stiff; pointed” (see my paper on the etymology of Gebeleixis): this Geb- is similar to English “jab” and to many other IE words, but is probably not exactly cognate to Ge/Gaia, but they both involve Ge=“hard”. Ancient Egyptian Geb (the name of their earth-god) may be akin, as may be Sumerian Ki=“earth”: but likely the similarities there come from a common human phono-semantic sound symbolism of word initial G and K and Kh having to do with earth and thick, strong, dense.

Part 8

In the Proto-Indo-European language, it has become clear they had a root **D^h*=“force, strength” as well as **teḱ-/ *tḱey-/ *tetḱ-* having the same meaning. They had other such words as well, but this section will not discuss them.

PIE **tḱey-*, “to cultivate; to settle; to live”, from this root derives Latin *sinō* (via **tḱi-né-ti*, denominative present of the root **tḱey-*); Latin *sinō*=“I put, lay, set down”, and the word also has other meanings which are not necessary to discuss at present. PIE **tḱey-*, “to cultivate; to settle; to live” is a reanalysed root of **tḱéyti*, from PIE **teḱ-*, “to sire, beget” (which led to **tetḱ-* “to create, produce, make”) plus *-éyti*²⁴ (the suffix forms aktionsart verbs from roots). All the meanings present in these roots derive from “force”: I’m not even going to bother to prove that. There is no other option.

Now I turn to some of the **D^h* roots. And again I do not care what others may think, it’s reality. I eventually learned that by trying other options and seeing that they didn’t work. PIE **d^her-* “to hold; hold fast, support”. PIE **d^herǵ^h-* “firm, strong, robust; support”. PIE **d^henh₂/*d^hen-* “to set in motion, to flow”: both meanings derive from “force; force applied”; PIE *d^hew-* “to run” leading to “to flow”: “to run” derives from “force/force applied”. I don’t care about objections to that theory, no objection will survive.

PIE **d^heh₁-* 1) “to do”; 2) “to put, place”: both meanings derive from “force” used in different ways: “to do”; “to put, place” originates from “to put firmly, to place firmly; to stand in place; upright”: all these meanings are implied/implicit, and they all derive from “force”.

PIE **d^hwes-* “to breathe (in or out); breath; spirit, soul>creature, animal, wild animal, etc.”: PIE **d^hwes-* derives from “force” specialized to “life-force”

24 Beekes, Robert, S. P. (2010), “κτίλος”, in *Etymological Dictionary of Greek* (Leiden Indo-European Etymological Dictionary Series; 10), volume I, with the assistance of Lucien van Beek, Leiden, Boston: Brill, → ISBN, page 792

and “breathing, breath”: the details have to be worked out, like how exactly does the “-wes” portion of this word function, an element which is most likely also seen in PIE **h*₂*wes*.

PIE **d^hewh*₂, “mist, smoke, haze” is from **d^hewh*₂=“thick, dense”, from **d^h-*=“force, strength, strong” leading to “thick, dense”, leading to “smoke, mist, haze”. PIE **d^heng^h-*, “to cover, overcast” also comes from **d^h-*=“thick, dense”, from **d^h-*=“force, strength, strong”.

PIE **d^hers-* “to be bold, to dare” is from “forceful”, from “force”.

There may have been a PIE **d^hāg-u-* “to whet, sharpen” source of Ancient Greek *θήγω*=“to whet, sharpen”---that root **d^hāg-u* meant “making strong”, making the tool have the ability to cut, stab, etc.

PIE **d^hewg^h-* “to produce; to produce something useful; to be strong, have force”: with “to produce something useful”, we see evidence for my explanation of PIE PIE **d^hāg-u-* “to whet, sharpen”: “make tools useful, make them have power, strength”>“to sharpen tools, whet tools”.

De Vaan in a recent work²⁵ has posited that PIE **d^heh*₁(*y*)- “to suckle, nurse” possibly/likely derives from PIE **d^heh*₁- “to do, put, place”: his paper gave me the idea that the two roots may be kindred; and they are kindred but I disagree about how they are kindred: I do not think that the meanings “to suck; suckle, nurse” derive from placing/putting the nipple in the baby’s mouth/placing the baby’s mouth on the nipple: I will posit instead that the meanings “to suckle, nurse” derive from the meanings “to suck” for which I posit three different derivations (and if De Vaan’s theory is wrong, then the etymology will be, most likely, one of the two that I posit): one theory I posit is that “to suck” derives from “to pull, drag” in turn from **d^h-*=“force, force employed”: see PIE **d^hreg^h*, “to run, to drag, to pull”, which is so similar to PIE **d^herǵ^h*, “bind fast; be firm; strong; robust”.

My second theory is that the meaning “to suck” for PIE **d^heh*₁(*y*)- derives from **d^h-*=“force” leading to “to flow>flow in” (and there was probably also an idea of the milk giving life-force, strength, to strengthen).

My third theory is that PIE **d^heh*₁(*y*)- “to suckle, nurse” derives from “to strengthen”, from **d^h-*=“force, strength”.

Lubotsky (2011: 122) posits that Sanskrit *didhaya* 1sg., Avestan *ā-didaia* ‘to consider, perceive’ with derived nouns such as Sanskrit *dhī-*, “vision, poetry, praise” and Avestan *daēna-* “view, creed” are explained from an i-perfect **d^hh*₁-*ói-*, **d^hh*₁-*i-* “to put”: Lubotsky states that the semantic change from “to put [a thought] into someone” (e.g., by the gods) to “inspire, reveal” is unproblematic.

25 De Vaan, Michiel. *On the Homonymy of “Put” and “Suck” in Proto-Indo-European*. Indo-European Linguistics 7. 2019. Brill.

Beekes (2010) and Forte (2015) point instead to Ancient Greek σῆμα (“sign”) and θέα (“view, sight”) and posit PIE *d^heh₂ (see also Ancient Greek θαῦμα “marvel; wonder; something strange”); while Sihler derives σῆμα from *d^hyeh₂-²⁶. If Lubotsky’s theory is incorrect, my equation *d^h=“force” can explain all those meanings cited in this paragraph in a number of different ways:

1) as deriving directly from the very early meaning of “force, power”: the power to use one’s mind to perceive, see, compose poetry, praise, consider; and then the meanings “sign”, “marvel” came from “to see, that which is seen”.

2) or the meanings came from “force” → “to grasp”,

3) or from “force” → “to draw, pull together” (compare PIE *leǵ- “to gather, collect” with derivatives meaning to speak).

4) Perhaps the most likely option is that the meanings derive from “to gather, condense, thicken, firm”, leading to “something clearly seen, clearly visible; to make out things easily because they are defined and substantial”, as I believe is the most likely explanation of PIE *h₂ew. “to see, perceive, hear; appear, manifest, obvious”.

PIE *d^héh₁s “god, deity; sacred place” may come from “force, strength” more than from any other meanings, though it may instead have meant mostly something else. Often words for “gods” means “givers, dispensers” (in this case

26 Sihler, Andrew (1995) *New Comparative Grammar of Greek and Latin*, Oxford, New York: Oxford University Press.

“placer(s)”? from “to put, place?”), but not sure if that is the main meaning for *d^héh₁s.

PIE *d^héǵhōm (“earth”) most likely derives from *d^héǵh= “firm, hard, thick, dense, covering, supporting”²⁷. PIE *d^héǵhōm is close to PIE *d^herǵh- “firm, strong, robust; support” and PIE *d^her- “to hold; hold fast, support”.

Also possible is that *d^héǵhōm meant “dry”, if cognate to PIE *d^heg^{wh}- “to burn; warm; hot”, and I believe that PIE *d^heg^{wh}- is possibly a combination of PIE **d^he- “breath, to breathe” in turn from “force, strength” and the suffixed “g^{wh}” sound(s) may have represented the back of the throat (the G sound is made towards the back of the throat or at least is perceived to be, hence “gurgle”, “gargle” etc.), because the back of the throat/back of the oral cavity is involved much more robustly in blowing out hot breath instead of cool breath.

Given the existence of PIE roots beginning with H denoting “hot, warm; burning; dry” (such as PIE *h₁ews) the scenario that I describe above is somewhat likely. But it may instead be that *d^heg^{wh}- “force, strength”+something else qualifying it: if it was a word for “fire” it could have had positive meaning, but since it meant more “to burn”---I’ll have to figure this one out next time.

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27 It has been posited by Frederik Kortlandt that PIE *(s)teg- “to cover” derives from the *d^héǵh- of *d^héǵhōm via devoicing of *d^h to *t via Siebs’ Law. See Kortlandt, Frederik (2014), “Proto-Indo-European “thorn”-clusters”, in *Historische Sprachforschung / Historical Linguistics, volume 127*. I’m sure that that is wrong. And that proposal is phonetically difficult. I think it’s most likely that PIE *(s)teg- “to cover; hide; obscure” derives from “a hardened, thickened, stiffened congelation/obscuration”/“a mass (of something on top of something else)” from the common PIE St=“stiff, hard, harsh, erect, pointed, firm”. That is better than supposing that the meaning “to cover” derives from “to project horizontally” or supposing that “to cover” derives from “roof”, in turn from “top”/“pointed top” with “top” deriving from “top of the stack, pile, pole” since there is another PIE *(s)teg- that means “pole, pillar; stack; pile”. It’s also possible (another theory I have) that the *d^héǵh of *d^héǵhōm meant “sprouting up, elevated, firm” referring to the firm dry land which is elevated above water and referring to the sprouting of plants, trees, hills and mountains and the sprouting of animals and people, etc. So in this scenario the earth would be “the Sprouting one”. For a time I liked the idea that the *d^héǵh in *d^héǵhōm meant “to flow, flowing” referring to the abundance of the earth, including in large part the plants and animals, via the common semantic progression “to flow>liquid, water>watery, moist>fat, sap (since fat is watery, moist and sap is flowing and liquefied before it sometimes hardens)”. But I think that the *d^héǵh in *d^héǵhōm meant “hard, firm, thick, covering, supporting”.

